

PROBLEMS OF UNEMPLOYMENT IN UZBEKISTAN AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM

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ABSTRACT

Achieving full employment of labor resources in the most important areas of social labor is a requirement of the time. Consequently, the regulation of the distribution of the population by industry also requires a lot of work to meet the needs of the population in certain types of activities at a certain historical stage. In this article, we want to take a look at the employment and labor market gaps in Uzbekistan.

It is known that employment is one of the most important macroeconomic indicators. At the same time, employment is social in nature. It reflects not only people's incomes, but also the need for self-expression through social activities, as well as the satisfaction of society with a certain level of socio-economic development. The need for paid work, the priority of socially useful activities, the criteria for participation in work, the choice of profession and place of work, the reason for work, interest in high-performance work and the ability to work on the basis of professional skills and ability to work - all of them arise as a result of a person's social orientation in society, financial, credit and distribution policy of the state, structural changes in the national economy, development of the service sector, education and health care. politics, etc. In

this regard, it is necessary to warn the population against mistakes, based on a simple understanding of the nature of employment. Employment is often defined as supply and demand for labor. When there is no unemployment, there are no unresolved employment problems. At the same time, the category of employment and the labor market are similar. The proposed economic program for overcoming the crisis does not take into account deep employment processes. For example, these processes are associated with the characteristics of the work of different socio-demographic groups, the level of education, social orientation, including the reason for the work, and so on. Considering employment as a problem of unemployment leads to an underestimation of the objective need for shifts in the use of labor resources, which

leads to a new approach to solving the problem of full and effective employment, achieving high levels of labor productivity and increasing employment, formation of a network structure: meeting the needs of the national labor force, taking into account its quantity and quality, improving the social and professional characteristics of labor resources, linking employment with the goals of demographic development. Since becoming independent, our country has undergone many reforms to achieve economic growth, economic freedom and development, as well as the fact that the achievement of economic stability is directly related to the employment of the unemployed in the country, that is, the low level of unemployment in the country means this economic development. It is now well known that many Uzbeks are looking for work abroad and work in other countries. In part, the number of citizens who went to work abroad amounted to 2 million people. This is 553.2 thousand less than in the first half of last year and 232 thousand less than in the first quarter of 2020. The number of people employed in the informal sector of the economy (excluding labor migrants working abroad) decreased by 2.1% or 105.3 thousand people compared to the end of 2019 and amounted to 5.1 million people. This is due to a decrease in the number of temporarily employed in one-time and seasonal work (108.4 thousand people), entrepreneurs working in the family business and without formalizing labor relations between entrepreneurs (87.4 thousand people), as well as unregistered entrepreneurs. The decrease was due to a reduction in the number (110.6 thousand people), explained in the Ministry of Labor. Due to the increase in the number of people living

at home during the quarantine period, and a sharp increase in the amount of subsidies from the Employment Assistance Fund for the development of private houses, the number of people employed in farms and private houses increased by 201.1 thousand people.

There are several reasons for the high unemployment rate in our country and the availability of able-bodied unemployed citizens, and in order to organize and search for solutions to these problems, it is necessary to study the socio-economic nature of employment and its concept. Therefore, the most important criterion for a socially oriented market economy is the attitude towards employment. Employment remains an integral part of comprehensive social policies. The social nature of the problem of employment is determined by the fact that it is primarily focused on a person, his interests and needs in the world of work. According to K.Kh. Kasimov, associate professor of economics, it is necessary to take into account at least four social aspects of employment:

1. The most important right to work, enshrined in the Constitution, is inextricably linked to the right to work. Currently, many people, consciously or unconsciously, associate employment with the possibility of realizing the right to work, and the problem of unemployment worries everyone;
2. The decisive role of employment in shaping the standard of living and decent living conditions. Increasing employment is currently the most important guarantee of improving the standard of living of able-bodied citizens and their families.
3. Formation of a new cause of highly productive labor, which is the basis for

improving the well-being of each person and society as a whole.

4. It is labor activity that changes a person, reveals and increases his professional potential, and stimulates personal development.

Together with other aspects of social policy, it should be considered as one of the main directions of employment development, which includes the redistribution of financial, material and labor resources in the national economy, determination of priorities for scientific and technological development. Also, ways are determined for the deployment of productive forces and improving the quality of life. This is one of the most important problems, and the solution to the problem of employment, and therefore the success of the reform of the entire economy, to some extent depends on the recognition and solution of this problem. In our opinion, the concept of employment is a system of views, ideas that reveal the nature of employment at a certain stage of the socio-economic development of society. The center of such theoretical understanding is the formation of employment, taking into account the objective processes of its development, which are characteristic of a social market type of state and are not limited by the real possibilities of achieving goals within a certain period of time. Society must provide a level playing field for everyone to realize their potential, but this depends on the individual qualities of a person in order to become an entrepreneur. The main features of employment in a socially oriented economy are: - a combination of full and efficient employment; - equal responsibility of the citizen and the state for the voluntariness of work and the

harmonization of human rights and obligations in the world of work, elimination of social dependence of employees, the opportunity to find a decent job; the reason for the free movement of labor between sectors, industries, professions and regions of labor consumption to increase labor productivity, a strong interest of entrepreneurship and employees in high productivity; mitigating the effects of a market economy with a clear goal for the benefit of workers. These features determine new qualitative characteristics of employment, the formation of which must be consistent with the corresponding employment policy. We consider employment policy as a set of measures that directly or indirectly affect the socio-economic development of society in order to achieve the set goals. In this case, the objectives of the employment policy should reflect the normative status of employment. This situation can be achieved by solving the problems of today. Employment policy has several levels: national, regional and local levels. Employment policies at all levels will provide for one-time employment, a concept that reflects the generally accepted type of economic development. Another principle of employment is that the state must create conditions for the realization of the right of citizens to work. Employment policy is based on the rejection of strict regulation, the optional nature of work in the social sphere, freedom and voluntariness to choose any area of socially useful work, as well as promoting the interests and needs of a person.

Here are the problems in the field of employment in Uzbekistan:

1. The inability of the unemployed population to meet the requirements of the labor market, that is, competition for vacancies in the labor market.

2. Insufficient social and political support for labor migrants wishing to work abroad.

To solve the problems listed above, we would like to make the following suggestions:

1. Improving the qualifications of the working-age population, training the working-age population in certain areas by expanding the sphere of secondary and higher education.

2. The complexity and contradictions of labor migration should objectively regulate this process and migration policy. There are different ways to define this concept, its goals and measure its effectiveness. As a rule, migration policy refers to specific measures that restrict or, conversely, encourage migration. There are direct and indirect methods. Direct methods of regulation include the allocation of funds for the movement of

migrants from one place to another, providing them with the necessary information.

In conclusion, if the unemployment rate in the country remains high, the outflow of citizens in search of work will continue to increase, which, in turn, will lead to a decrease in the "mental" and "physical" labor resources in the country. As a result of these factors, the share of the country's GDP decreases, economic instability and socio-economic efficiency decrease. Therefore, in order to at least partially reduce the number of unemployed, expand and continue preferential bank loans provided to the population under the programs "Every family is an entrepreneur", "Support for youth entrepreneurship", as well as the desire to remain unemployed and work in agriculture. We believe that it is necessary annually carry out such work as the allocation of a certain part of the lease agreement to citizens on an ongoing basis.

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